

INFLUENCE OF FIBER ORIENTATION RECONSTRUCTION ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the influence of the reconstruction method of the fiber orientation density function (ODF) from a fiber orientation tensor, on the mechanical load capacity, is investigated using representative volume elements (RVEs). First, the ODFs are reconstructed by the spherical harmonics approach as well as by the method of maximum entropy from a 2nd order fiber orientation tensor. Subsequently, RVE's are generated taking into account the ODF and a fiber length distribution. As the number of fibers in one RVE is limited by computing capacity, the ODF in the RVE is not the same as the ODF from the reconstruction. Therefore, it is investigated how many fibers are necessary to make the RVE representative in the sense of the fiber orientation.

Finally, a comparison of the mechanical stresses allows to analyse the influence of the reconstruction methods on the numerical evaluation of the effective composite properties. The effective stiffness of the composite in the principal direction of the 2nd order orientation tensor is higher if the ODF is reconstructed by the maximum entropy method. This is due to a greater alignment of the fibers. The mechanical load capacity, on the other hand, is on average roughly the same with both reconstruction methods. However, the standard deviation of the mechanical load capacity is greater with the maximum entropy method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short fiber-reinforced plastics are ideal materials for high-performance lightweight applications. The numerical analysis of such components requires exact knowledge of the mechanical properties of the composite. This is a great challenge, especially due to the locally different microstructure. The microstructure is strongly influenced by the manufacturing process, such as injection molding. The fiber orientation of the short fiber-reinforced composite varies at every point of the component depending on the flow conditions of the manufacturing process. Therefore, it is obvious to describe the mechanical behavior of the component in dependency of the microstructure. Consequently, the more precisely the microstructure can be modelled, the more precisely the mechanical design of the molded part can be performed. Due to the enormous numerical effort, the fiber orientation in injection molding simulations is greatly simplified. Reconstruction methods are used to recover the original fiber orientation in a post processing step from the orientation tensor.

This paper examines the effect of different reconstruction methods on the effective composite properties. For this purpose, the two reconstruction methods *Maximum Entropy* and *Spherical harmonics* are introduced and used to create representative volume elements (RVE). The RVEs are then used to determine the effective composite properties. By comparing the calculated composite properties, the influence of the reconstruction methods can be investigated.

2 RECONSTRUCTION OF FIBER ORIENTATION

The orientation of a single fiber can be described by the direction vector \mathbf{p} on a unit sphere. The orientation of many fibers can be represented by the orientation density function (ODF) ψ . The ODF

represents the probability of a fiber lying in a certain direction, as shown in figure 1. The ODF can be calculated using the Fokker-Plank equation

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \cdot (\mathbf{u}\psi) + \nabla_{\mathbf{p}} \cdot (\dot{\mathbf{p}}\psi) = \Delta_{\mathbf{p}}(D_r\psi) \quad (1)$$

In equation 1, the ODF is calculated on the basis of the flow conditions [1]. But due to the high effort required to solve the Fokker-Plank equation, the Folgar-Tucker equation [2, 3]

$$\frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{2}(\omega_{ik} \cdot a_{kj} - a_{ik} \cdot \omega_{kj}) + \frac{\lambda}{2}[\varepsilon_{ik} \cdot a_{kj} + a_{ik} \cdot \varepsilon_{kj} - 2\varepsilon_{kl}a_{ijkl}] + 2D_r(\delta_{ij} - 3a_{ij}) \quad (2)$$

is used in commercial injection moulding simulations using a spectral decomposition of the ODF. In a spectral decomposition, the ODF is approximated by a series of orientation tensors [4]:

$$\mathbf{a}_n = a_{ij\dots} = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi} p_i p_j p_{\dots} \psi(\theta, \Phi) \sin \theta d\theta d\Phi \quad (3)$$

Reconstruction methods can be used to back-calculate the ODF from given orientation tensors. In this paper the reconstruction using spherical harmonics and the method of maximum entropy is considered. Both reconstruction methods are presented in the following.

2.1 Spherical Harmonics

Reconstruction with spherical harmonics is accomplished by summing the moments α_l [4]:

$$\hat{\psi}_N(\theta, \Phi) = \sum_{l=0}^N \alpha_l(\theta, \Phi). \quad (4)$$

The moments α_l are composed by

$$\alpha_l(\theta, \Phi) = \sum_{m=0}^l \beta_l^m(\theta, \Phi) \quad (5)$$

with

$$\beta_l^m(\theta, \Phi) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\delta_{m0}\right) \left(\frac{1}{\pi} P_l^m(\cos \theta) \cos(m\Phi) \oint_{\mathbb{S}} \psi(\theta, \Phi) P_l^m(\cos \theta) \cos(m\Phi) dS \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{\pi} P_l^m(\cos \theta) \sin(m\Phi) \oint_{\mathbb{S}} \psi(\theta, \Phi) P_l^m(\cos \theta) \sin(m\Phi) dS \right) \quad (6)$$

and

$$P_l^m(\mu) = (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{2l+1}{2} \frac{(l-m)!}{(l+m)!} \frac{1}{2^l \cdot l!}} (1-\mu^2)^{\frac{m}{2}} \frac{d^{m+l}(\mu^2-1)^l}{d\mu^{m+l}} \quad (7)$$

For the reconstruction it is necessary to replace the integral terms of equation 6 by the corresponding entries of the fiber orientation tensors according to definition 3. Therefore, the sum of moments can only be calculated as far as fiber orientation tensors are available. Usually, for a reconstruction problem only the second order fiber orientation tensor \mathbf{a}_2 is available [5]. However, so-called closures can still be used, from which fiber orientation tensor of a higher order can be calculated [2]. A frequently used closure is the hybrid closure [3], which is entirely used in this paper. The hybrid closure

$$\mathbf{a}_4^{hyb} = (1-f)\mathbf{a}_4^{lin} + \mathbf{a}_4^{qud} \quad (8)$$

consists of the linear closure

$$\mathbf{a}_4^{lin} = -\frac{1}{35}(\delta_{ij}\delta_{kl} + \delta_{ik}\delta_{jl} + \delta_{il}\delta_{jk}) \\ + \frac{1}{7}(a_{ij}\delta_{kl} + a_{ik}\delta_{jl} + a_{il}\delta_{jk} + a_{kl}\delta_{ij} + a_{jl}\delta_{ik} + a_{jk}\delta_{il}) \quad (9)$$

and the quadratic closure

$$\mathbf{a}_4^{qud} = a_{ij}a_{kl} \quad (10)$$

with

$$f = \frac{3}{2}a_{ij}a_{ij} - \frac{1}{2}. \quad (11)$$

2.1 Method of Maximum Entropy

Another method of reconstructing an ODF is the method of maximum entropy. In equation 12 a Bingham distribution, defined by [6]

$$f(\bar{x}) = e^{-\alpha\bar{x}_1^2 + \beta\bar{x}_3^2}, \quad (12)$$

is iteratively adapted. The assumption that the ODF has a Bingham distribution is based on the work of Hine et. al, who confirm on the basis of experimental measurements that real distribution functions do have Bingham distributed fiber orientations [7]. The adaptation of the Bingham distribution is performed in such a way that the second order fiber orientation tensor of the ODF with the Bingham distribution is identical to a given second order fiber orientation tensor. From this approach, a minimization problem can be defined:

$$f(x) = (d_{ix}w_i - a_{xx})^2 + (d_{iy}w_i - a_{yy})^2 + (d_{iz}w_i - a_{zz})^2. \quad (13)$$

Index i refers to a normal direction of a discretized unit sphere. This paper uses an icosphere discretization [8] with a total of 20480 triangles. Furthermore, is

$$w_i = J_i e^{(x_j d_{ij} + x_4)} \quad (14)$$

with

$$d_{ij} = \bar{p}_{ij}^2 \quad (15)$$

and

$$\bar{p}_{ij} = R \cdot p_{ij}. \quad (16)$$

R is the rotation matrix used to rotate the icosphere into the main axis system of the fiber orientation tensor. The minimization problem can be solved with suitable numerical methods. Sequential Least Square Programming (SLSQP) [9] is used in this work.

2.1 Testcase

For the comparison between the reconstruction methods a second order fiber orientation tensor

$$\mathbf{a}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.8 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

is considered. An ODF is calculated with both reconstruction methods. Within the spherical harmonics approach the fourth ordered fiber orientation tensor, which is determined with the hybrid closure, is taken into account. Both ODFs are shown next to each other in figure 1. Shown is the used unit sphere for the reconstruction with a color representation of the probability that a fiber is pointing in a certain direction. Red means a high probability, blue a low probability. It is obvious that the ODF reconstructed by both methods are different. The reconstructed distribution with the spherical harmonics is much wider. This is due to the fact that only the second and fourth stage fiber orientation tensors are used for the reconstruction and therefore sharp limited distributions can't be represented.

Figure 1: Reconstruction of the ODF using Spherical Harmonics and the Maximum Entropy Method

3 REPRESENTATIVE VOLUME ELEMENTS

One method to determine the mechanical composite properties is to calculate the local material stressing on a microscale using the finite element method in representative volume elements. In RVE's any aspects of the microstructure can be investigated. This section explains the modelling of the RVE and the usage of Monte-Carlo simulations in this paper.

3.1 Creation of RVEs

Figure 2 shows the principle of the modelling and usage of the finite element method. The microstructure of the composite is created as a periodic 3D model. The periodicity is a prerequisite for periodic boundary conditions with which boundary effects are minimized [10]. By applying a global deformation, locally resulting stresses or strains can be analysed. Moreover, the mechanical properties of the matrix material and the fibers are required. Here, the matrix is defined as isotropic, linear elastic with $E_m = 2.100 \text{ MPa}$ and $\mu_m = 0.42$. The fibers are also isotropic, linear elastic with $E_m = 70.000 \text{ MPa}$ and $\mu_m = 0.2$.

Figure 2: 3D model and FEM solution of a RVE with periodic microstructure

Using a homogenization scheme, the effective stiffness is calculated from the local stresses σ_{ij}^l and strains ε_{ij}^l . Therefore, the effective mean stress σ_{ij}^* is calculated with

$$\sigma_{ij}^* = \frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \sum_{I=1}^{n_{int}} \sigma_{ij}^I \cdot V^I \quad (18)$$

and the effective mean strain with

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^* = \frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \sum_{I=1}^{n_{int}} \varepsilon_{ij}^I \cdot V^I. \quad (19)$$

In both equation V^I is the integration volume of the node I and V_{RVE} the volume of the RVE. This allows the effective stiffness to be calculated in the direction of the applied global deformation (here in the 2-direction) with

$$E_{22} = \frac{\sigma_{22}^*}{\varepsilon_{22}^*}. \quad (20)$$

In the context of this work a tensile deformation is used only. The two direction is the direction of the largest eigenvalue of the considered fiber orientation tensor. Accordingly, the tensile deformation in the RVE is in the primary direction of the fibers.

To create the 3D model of the RVE, a sample of n fibers is taken from the ODF. Figure 3 shows the resulting fiber orientation on a unit sphere for $n = 100$, 1000 and $10,000$. This figure shows that the reconstructed ODF and the sample drawn from it can differ qualitatively considerably from each other. The second order fiber orientation tensor calculated from the sample is correspondingly different from the given tensor and converges only slowly with an increasing number of fibers. In principle, it is equivalent to create a sample with n fibers or to superimpose m samples with n/m fibers. This is important because the number of fibers that can be considered in the RVE is limited due to the high numerical effort.

Figure 3: Sampling of the ODF reconstructed by spherical harmonics with 100, 1000 and 10,000 fibers considered

In addition to fiber orientation, a fiber length distribution is measured from injection molded sample and used to model the microstructure. The fiber length distribution is shown in Figure 4. The mean length of this distribution is 212 μm . The diameter of the fibers is constant with 11.6 μm .

Figure 4: Fiber length distribution used for the investigation

3.2 Monte-Carlo Simulation of RVE

Monte-Carlo simulations, in which the positions of the fibers within the representative volume elements are varied, show that the stress distribution depends on the local arrangement of the fibers. Therefore, the mechanical stress distribution is unique for each fiber constellation. For this reason, a convergence study with the method of maximum entropy for fiber orientation will be carried out. First, more than 100 RVEs are realized for 50 and 100 fibers and the effective stiffness in the principal direction of the fiber orientation tensor is calculated according to equation 20. Figure 5 shows the resulting stiffness distribution. This stiffness distribution can be described very well with a normal distribution. For both 50 and 100 fibers, the mean value is equal to 5300 MPa. The standard deviation is greater for 50 fibers than for 100 fibers. This can be explained by the fact that with more fibers, fiber constellations that lead to particularly high or low stresses have less influence on the stiffness of a single RVE, since the fraction of participating fibers of that specific constellation is lower than for RVE with fewer fibers.

Figure 5: Histogram and fitted normal distribution of effective stiffness for RVE with fiber orientation reconstructed by the method of maximum entropy.

Based on the convergence study carried out, the relative sample standard deviation σ_{MC} of the Monte-Carlo simulation can be determined with

$$\sigma_{MC} = \frac{\sigma_{RVE}}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (21)$$

Here, n is the number of RVE's under consideration and σ_{RVE} is the standard deviation of the RVEs. From this it can be derived how many RVE's have to be considered, so that the relative sample standard deviation σ_{MC} is lower than required. For this study, it should be less than 0.5%, so that 100 RVE's with 100 fibers each are considered for the investigation of the influence of the reconstruction method.

Figure 6: Diagram of the relative standard error of the effective stiffness for 50 and 100 fibers as a function of the number of RVEs considered

4 INFLUENCE OF ODF RECONSTRUCTION

In this section, the influence of the reconstruction method on the effective composite properties is investigated. For this purpose, Monte-Carlo simulations are carried out with reconstructions, using the method of maximum entropy and spherical harmonics, of the test scenario described in section 2.1.

First, the effective stiffness is analyzed. For this purpose, the effective Young's modulus in the principal direction of the fiber orientation tensor (here the 2-direction, cf. 3.1) is evaluated and shown as a box plot in Figure 7 for both reconstruction methods. Obviously, the mean value of the stiffness with the maximum entropy method is considerably higher than the mean value with the spherical harmonics reconstruction. This is due to the greater alignment of the fibers (see Figure 1). With the maximum entropy method, the fibers are more often oriented in the primary direction, so that the effective Young's modulus is higher. Also of interest is the scattering of the effective stiffness, which is relatively similar in both methods, although the scattering of the fiber orientation deviates more significantly with the reconstruction using spherical harmonics. The scattering of the fiber orientation does not seem to affect the scattering of the effective Young's modulus in this example.

Figure 7: Boxplot of effective Modulus in direction of fiber reinforcement for the Maximum Entropy and the Spherical Harmonics reconstruction method.

In addition to the effective stiffness, the maximum load capacity is investigated. For this purpose, a damage hypothesis is defined with which the maximum load capacity can be determined. Composite failure is assumed as soon as the average loading of the RVE exceeds a critical value. In the context of this paper, the Von-Mises stress of the matrix material is chosen as the criterion. The maximum loading capacity is therefore

$$\langle \sigma_{M,max} \rangle = \frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \sigma_M^I \cdot V^I < \sigma_{M,crit} \quad (22)$$

with $\sigma_{M,crit}$ the critical Von-Mises value of the unreinforced matrix material. This value is determined to 47.5 MPa using tensile tests on injection-molded specimens. Figure 8 shows the calculated mechanical load capacity as a box plot. It is given as the global strain value above which the critical Von-Mises stress value is exceeded. With 2.19% and 2.2% strain, the difference of the mean value with both reconstruction methods is negligible. The standard deviation, on the other hand, is considerable greater with the maximum entropy method than with the spherical harmonics reconstruction. Similar to the effective stiffness, it is not possible to deduce the scatter of the maximum loading capacity from the scatter of the ODF.

Figure 8: Boxplot of the effective mechanical load capacity in direction of fiber reinforcement for the Maximum Entropy and the Spherical Harmonics reconstruction method.

To explain the greater scatter, the Von-Mises stress distribution at 1% global strain is shown in Figure 9. It is shown that with the method of Maximum Entropy the distribution is wider, recognizable at about 18 and 40 MPa. This suggests that with the reconstruction of the Maximum Entropy it is more likely to generate fiber constellations leading to both higher and lower stresses in the matrix. Correspondingly, the greater scatter of the maximum loading capacity can be explained.

Figure 9: Distribution of Von-Mises stress at 1% global strain

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper examines the influence of the ODF reconstruction method on the effective composite properties. For this purpose, Monte-Carlo simulations of RVEs with the two considered reconstruction methods are performed and evaluated on the basis of a test scenario.

The reconstruction with the maximum entropy method produces an ODF with a more unidirectional distribution than the reconstruction with spherical harmonics. The effective properties of the considered

RVE differ considerably. Accordingly, the reconstruction method is important for the calculation of the effective composite properties.

- Effective stiffness with the method of maximum entropy is approx. 20% higher
- Scatter of the effective stiffness is equal for both methods
- Mean value of the maximum load capacity are with both methods similarly
- Scatter of load capacity with method of maximum entropy is greater

According to the influence of the reconstruction method shown here, the choice of the reconstruction method is important for the calculation of effective composite properties and therefore important for the component design. On the basis of the scenario of the two-stage fiber orientation tensor shown here, no statement can be made as to whether one reconstruction method is superior to the other in terms of accuracy. Future studies must therefore show which method is better for reconstructing an ODF.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Helzel, F. Otto, Multiscale simulations for suspensions of rod-like molecules, *Journal of Computational Physics* 216 (2006) 52–75.
- [2] F. Folgar, C.L. Tucker, Orientation Behavior of Fibers in Concentrated Suspensions, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 3 (1984) 98–119.
- [3] S.G. Advani, C.L. Tucker, The Use of Tensors to Describe and Predict Fiber Orientation in Short Fiber Composites, *Journal of Rheology* 31 (1987) 751–784.
- [4] David Abram Jack, Advanced Analysis of short fiber polymer composite material behavior.
- [5] Information on <http://help.autodesk.com/view/MFIWS/2014/ENU/?guid=GUID-6B3A7386-DE57-450E-BF94-B10BD629EC9B>
- [6] C. Bingham, An Antipodally Symmetric Distribution on the Sphere, *Ann. Statist.* 2 (1974) 1201–1225.
- [7] P.J. Hine, H.R. Lusti, A.A. Gusev, On the possibility of reduced variable predictions for the thermoelastic properties of short fibre composites, *Composites Science and Technology* 64 (2004) 1081–1088.
- [8] Information on http://www.songho.ca/opengl/gl_sphere.html
- [9] D. Kraft, A software package for sequential quadratic programming, 1988.
- [10] V.-D. Nguyen, E. Béchet, C. Geuzaine, L. Noels, Imposing periodic boundary condition on arbitrary meshes by polynomial interpolation, *Computational Materials Science* 55 (2012) 390–406.